

Youth Info Survey 2025: Mobility and the Role of Youth Information

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1. What is the Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025?

The Eurodesk Youth Info Surveys are conducted regularly in order to provide insights into the domain of youth mobility information. The previous surveys were conducted in 2017 ([Sabuni 2018](#)), in 2019 ([Sabuni 2019](#)), in 2022 ([Bárta 2022](#)), and this latest one in 2024 ([Bárta 2025](#)).

The full international report, titled [Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025](#) (further referred to as the main report 2025), has already been published, and we invite you to browse through it online or in a hard copy, as it provides insights from 7144 respondents between 13 and 35 years of age residing in one of the countries of the EU mobility schemes, such as Erasmus+ or the European Solidarity Corps.

This report does not reiterate the general findings from the main report 2025; it focuses solely on exploring views of the 1878 young people from Germany who filled in the survey. Its purpose is to identify their specific needs and experiences, as well as the challenges they face. This is achieved by comparing the German youth with the young people from all other countries, and by presenting Germany-specific summary results. Comparing these two groups shows in what areas the German young people voice the same opinions as their peers from other countries, and where their views differ, while the summary results provide an overview of results focusing solely on German youth¹.

It needs to be noted that while the German sample is very similar in terms of respondent backgrounds (e.g., minority background, size of settlement where young people lived, etc.), to the overall sample of young people from other countries, there is one exception which may have affected the results presented in this report. The German sample consist almost exclusively of young people aged 16 to 23. A Sample of young people from other countries also includes young people 13-15 years old (6% in comparison with 0% in case of the German sample), and young people 24-35 years old (26% in comparison with 3% in the German sample). It is therefore reasonable to read this report as only relating to German young people aged 16 to 23, and to keep this in mind when considering any differences presented therein.

This differences in the age profile of the European sample and the German national sample might have resulted from the way the respondents were recruited for the survey in Germany. Eurodesk Germany promoted the survey in its [newsletter for young people](#). The newsletter statistics show that 2,463 young people clicked on the link to the survey, suggesting many of the respondents indeed came from the group of the newsletter recipients. The Eurodesk Germany newsletter started in 2022 and mainly consists of young people who applied to [DiscoverEU tickets](#) and subscribed to the newsletter for more information. The young people are mostly eighteen when they apply to DiscoverEU, with a new cohort added each year. Therefore, young people subscribing for the Eurodesk Germany newsletter would be largely in the age group of 18-20 in 2024 when the survey was conducted, influencing the age profile of the German national sample.

The findings of this report aim to help youth information services better tailor their approach, thereby improving information delivery and mobility experience of the German youth.

¹ All results are rounded to the nearest whole number, and the graphs featured in this report only show results where the differences between the German youth and their peers from other countries are statistically significant.

2. What do German Young People think about mobility?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on mobility in general. For overall results, refer to [the main report 2025](#).

Young Germans are just as open to going abroad as their peers from other countries (about 69% of them are very open to going abroad, and additional 29% are open to it). Young Germans are, however, more discouraged from going abroad by climate change concerns (see Figure 1), with 41% of them stating climate change concerns in comparison with only 29% of their peers from other countries. Youth information services should use this finding and place a corresponding emphasis on sharing information about green travel options and other ways of mitigating the environmental impact of mobility, as this might encourage more German young people to seek mobility experiences.

Figure 1: Climate change concerns in the mobility context, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Beneficial impacts of mobility

Both young Germans and their peers from other countries consider a mobility experience to be beneficial to their continuous education (about 98%). German youth, however, are less enthusiastic about the benefits of the mobility experiences to their personal and professional lives (see Figure 2). While the overall rates of appreciation of mobility experiences for personal and professional lives are similarly high in the group of German youth and in the group of their peers from other countries (over 95% for both the German youth and those from other countries), German young people are less prone to enthusiasm, with 52% of them stating they believe mobility experience to be very positive to their personal life (in comparison with 62% in their peers from other countries), and 42% of them seeing very positive benefits for their professional life (in contrast to 62% in their peers from other countries). Youth information services may use these findings for example by sharing real life examples or research proof of positive impacts of mobilities on various aspects of young people's lives.

Figure 2: Perceived benefits of mobility experiences, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Preferred mobility activities

All in all, German youth is most interested in traveling, followed by doing internships, working, and studying (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Summary overview of overall interest in various mobility activities among German youth.

To travel	99%
To do an internship	83%
To work	80%
To study	79%
To attend a youth exchange or summer camp	71%
To attend a training course	70%
To volunteer	68%
To do seasonal work	63%

Note: Sum of "Very interested" and "Interested" options is used as the indicator of the overall agreement. The question read "What would you like to do abroad?".

When it comes to different mobility activities, young Germans are just as enthusiastic about studying and internships as their peers from other countries (about 80% and about 83% would be very interested or interested, respectively). The only mobility format in which young Germans are

more enthusiastic than their peers from other countries is about going abroad to travel (90% are very interested in comparison with 84% in their peers from other countries). In all other mobility formats, young Germans are less interested than their peers from other countries (see Figure 4 and Figure 5). The largest difference shows in the case of youth exchanges and summer camps (the overall interest of 71% in contrast to 81% of their international peers) and training courses (the overall interest of 69% compared to 85% in other nations).

These are interesting results, and youth information services may utilise the high interest in traveling as such to boost interest in many other mobility formats, as travels are an integral part of any mobility experience. Youth exchanges and summer camps, for example, offer plenty of opportunities to travel around and meet up young people from other countries.

Figure 4: Interest in various mobility activities, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries, part I.

Figure 5: Interest in various mobility activities, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries, part II.

Length of mobility

When it comes to length of mobility, the most popular mobility lengths among German youth are 3 months, half a year, and one month (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Summary overview of overall interest in mobility lengths among German youth.

about 3 months	87%
about half a year	86%
about 1 month	82%
a few days or 1 week	70%
1 year or longer	63%

Note: Sum of "Very interested" and "Interested" options is used as the indicator of the overall agreement. The question read "How long would you be interested in going abroad for?".

German young people are just as interested in going abroad for a year as their peers from other countries (the overall interest level of about 63%), but they are more prone to going abroad for half a year (the overall interest of about 86% in comparison with 75% in their peers from other countries; see Figure 7) and for 3 months (the overall interest is about 87% in contrast to peers abroad who show about 82% of interest). When it comes to the shorter mobility formats, German young people are less interested than their peers in both a month long mobility (the percentage interested is about 82%, relative to about 85% among peers from other countries) and a week or

days-long mobilities (the overall interest of about 70% in comparison with about 82% in their peers from other countries).

Figure 7: Interest in mobility lengths, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

The information services may use this finding to focus more on sharing more information on advantages and opportunities for year-long mobilities and on the short ones of a week or a few days to encourage German youth to use these formats. Given the high preferences of German youth in doing internships, working, or studying (see previous graphs), young people from Germany might indeed be interested in the long-term formats of a year or so, when the advantages are clearly outlined for them.

Preferred mobility formats

Young people from Germany align with their peers in preferences of the mobility options. They most prefer the in-person experiences, are somewhat interested in hybrid ones, and very little interested in the virtual mobilities. Figure 8 shows that German young people are even more interested in the in-person mobilities than their peers from other countries, but they are significantly less interested than their peers in hybrid experiences (the proportion of respondents interested is about 52%, compared with about 70% among peers abroad), and in virtual mobilities (the overall interest of about 17% in comparison with about 36% in their peers from other countries).

Figure 8: Interest in mobility options, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

3. How do German young people learn about mobility?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on their information needs related to mobility. For overall results, refer to [the main report 2025](#). About half of the young people from Germany visited the website of the German Eurodesk office (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Awareness of the website of the German Eurodesk office among German youth.

German young people do not differ from their peers from other countries in their experience with searching for mobility-related information, as about 76% of them have already tried searching for such information. The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided both groups of young people (those with and those without the experience on searching for mobility-related information) with an opportunity to share the information sources they used.

Preference of sources

Figure 10 and Figure 11 summarise the overall results for German young people without and with experience of searching for mobility-related information. It is apparent that those with and those without search experience align on the most popular sources of information. In both groups, web search is by far the most likely source of mobility-related information for German youth, followed by friends and family, social media, and schools or universities.

Figure 10: Summary overview of overall agreement on usage of potential sources of mobility-related information among German youth with no search experience.

Web search	99%
Friends and family	91%
Social media	89%
School / university	86%
Regional and National Youth Portal(s)	74%
Eurodesk	74%
European Youth Portal	67%
Youth information centres or services	51%
Youth club / organisation	40%
EuropeDirect	31%
EURES	30%

Note: Sum of "Very likely" and "Likely" options is used as the indicator of the overall agreement. The question read "If you wanted to learn more about mobility opportunities, would you turn to the following sources?".

Figure 11: Summary overview of usage of sources of mobility-related information used by German youth with search experience.

Web search	99%
Friends and family	87%
School / university	82%
Social media	82%
Eurodesk	63%
European Youth Portal	56%
Regional and National Youth Portal(s)	28%
Youth information centres or services	24%
Youth club / organisation	24%
EuropeDirect	7%
EURES	4%

Note: Percentages refer to the shares of respondents answering “Yes” to a question “What sources of information about mobility opportunities have you used?”.

Let’s first have a more detailed look at the young people who did not try searching for mobility-related information yet. Among those who did not yet try to search for mobility-related information, the following potential sources of information do not differ between the German youth and their peers from other countries: social media (about 89% overall agree they are willing to use it), regional youth portals (about 75% across the respondents indicate that they would use it), and the European Youth Portal (about 67% overall state they would use it). Schools and universities are almost as likely to be used by German youth as by their peers from other countries (about 86% overall agree in comparison with 89%, respectively). A similar result can be seen in case of friends and family (about 90% of German youth overall agree, in comparison with about 87% of their peers from other countries) and in case of a web search (about 99% of German youth overall agree, compared to about 98% of their peers from other countries).

Figure 12: Potential sources of mobility-related information, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with no search experience, part I.

Figure 13: Potential sources of mobility-related information, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with no search experience, part II.

The only source of information that German young people with no experience of searching for mobility-related information saw as more likely to use than their peers from other countries was Eurodesk (about 74% overall agree in comparison with 63%, respectively; see Figure 12). This is a positive result, as it indeed places the German Eurodesk office among the highly relevant potential information sources.

On the other hand, there are many information sources which German young people marked as less likely to use than their peers from other countries (see Figure 13). EURES and Europe Direct would be used by about 30% of the German youth in contrast to 43% of their peers in Europe. Youth clubs or youth organisations would be used by about 40% of German youth, compared with 70% of their peers from other countries. Lastly, youth information centres or services, the use rate is the highest with about 51% for Germans versus 72% youth abroad. These information sources either need boost in awareness among young Germans, or they are less likely to be effective or efficient in delivering mobility information.

Let's now have a more detailed look at the young people who already did try searching for mobility-related information. Almost all young people from Germany as well as their peers from other countries used web search (99% and 98%, respectively). Young people from Germany were more likely to use some information sources than their peers from other countries (see Figure 14), namely: friends and family (87% in comparison with 72% in their peers from other countries), Eurodesk (63% versus 54% among their peers in Europe), and schools or universities (82% while their peers from other countries report 78%). There are also information sources which German young people used less than their counterparts from other countries, namely (see Figure 15 and Figure 16): youth information centres or services, youth clubs or organisations, EURES, European Youth Portal, regional or national youth portals, Europe Direct, and social media.

All the information in this section is useful to the youth information services mostly in strategic planning. While some information campaigns can be planned internationally and German young people are just as likely to be reached via certain information sources, some are better planned nationally, as in some cases usage of information sources can differ substantially.

Figure 14: Usage of sources of mobility-related information, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with search experience, part I.

Figure 15: Usage of sources of mobility-related information, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with search experience, part II.

Figure 16: Usage of sources of mobility-related information, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with search experience, part III.

Usefulness of sources and topics

Acknowledging that not all information sources need to be perceived as useful by young people, the Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 asked young people to rate usefulness of various information sources.

All in all, there are six information sources which are rated as very useful by German youth (see Figure 17). These are videos, school or university events or services, specialised websites, social

media, peers and classmates, and family and relatives. The information sources used the least by young Germans are radio and television, and messaging apps.

Figure 17: Summary overview of overall usefulness of information sources, among German youth.

· Videos	91%
· School / university events / services	91%
· Specialised websites	89%
· Social media	88%
· Peers / classmates	87%
· Family / relatives	87%
· Stands / presentations in fairs, events, concerts	80%
· Colleagues / employers	78%
· Flyers/posters	73%
· Emails with updates / eNewsletters	67%
· Online seminars / webinars	64%
· Mobility advisors / counsellors	58%
· Magazines / newspapers	47%
· Radio / TV	40%
· Messaging apps	31%

Note: Sum of "Very useful" and "Useful" options is used as the indicator of the overall usefulness. The question read "How would you rate the usefulness of receiving information about mobility opportunities from the following sources?".

German young people rate usefulness of the following information sources the same as their counterparts from other countries: Only 40% of respondents consider radio or television as useful, while about 87% evaluate family and peers as useful. 91% rate school or university events and services as practical as well as videos.

Some of the information sources are rated very similarly by the German youth and their peers from other countries, such as videos (about 91% of the Germans and 85% of their European peers rate as useful), stands or presentations at fairs or events (about 80% rate them as useful compared with about 81% among their international peers), social media (about 88% of the Germans agreed in contrast to 92% on European level), peers or classmates (about 88% agreement rate compared to 83% on European level), online seminars or webinars (about 64% of respondents consider it useful versus about 71% of peers abroad.), and emails with updates or e-newsletters (about 66% rate as overall useful in comparison with about 74% in their peers from other countries).

Some of the information sources are rated as more useful by German youth next to their peers from other European countries. 73% of the Germans and 60% of their peers evaluate flyers and posters as useful, while 47% of the German respondents and 34% of the European ones rate magazines or newspapers as helpful. 87% of the Germans and 76% of their peers would consider family and relatives as a helpful source.

There are two sources of information which are rated by German youth as significantly less useful, compared to their counterparts from other countries (see Figure 18). These are messaging apps (only about 31% value them as useful compared to about 58% on the European level), and mobility advisors or counsellors (about 58% rate as overall useful in contrast to about 75% in their peers from other countries).

Figure 18: Usefulness of information sources, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries with search experience.

Exploring further the information needs of young people in the mobility domain, the Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 offered an opportunity to rate usefulness of various types of information related to learning mobilities. There are only very slight differences in the priorities shared by German youth and priorities outlined by their peers from other countries, and the overall summary (see Figure 19) shows that all of the information types are rated as highly useful by German youth.

Figure 19: Summary overview of overall usefulness of information types, among German youth.

Financial information (e.g. grants, scholarships)	98%
Specific mobility opportunities you can participate in	95%
Personalised support / guidance to find the right opportunity and/or prepare your application	89%
Support upon returning to your home country (e.g. getting credit for the skills you learned)	88%
Possibility to connect with other young people who went abroad or are planning to go	87%
Real stories from young people who went abroad	86%
Travel preparation (e.g. what to pack, what to expect)	84%

Note: Sum of "Very useful" and "Useful" options is used as the indicator of the overall usefulness. The question read "What kind of information related to going abroad would you find helpful to receive?".

Furthermore, young people were also invited to share their views on the usefulness of different methods of receiving information. In this case, similarly to the one above, German youth does not significantly differ from their peers in other countries. The summary overview (see Figure 20)

shows that while online platforms are seen as the most useful by German youth, they also appreciate hearing stories of their peers who already went abroad for a mobility period, and they also see workshops and information sessions at schools as useful formats. About two thirds of German youth also appreciate information centres and personalised support.

Figure 20: Summary overview of overall usefulness of methods of receiving information, among German youth.

Online platform to search for different opportunities in one place	92,30%
Hear from other young people who have already been abroad	88,00%
Workshops and information sessions at school/university	87,10%
Having an information centre nearby that provides information and personalised support	67,80%

Note: Sum of "Very useful" and "Useful" options is used as the indicator of the overall usefulness. The question read "How useful are the following methods for receiving information about mobility opportunities?".

General online search preference

Young people also shared their preferences when it comes to searching information in the online environment. All in all, almost all German young people browse websites, and a vast majority also watches videos, and checks out social media (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Summary overview of overall preferences of searching for information in the online environment, among German youth.

I check out websites	99%
I watch long videos (3 or more minutes) to learn about new things	89%
I watch short videos (under 3 minutes) for in-depth information	89%
I check out social media	88%
I follow organisations / brands	74%
I follow people / influencers	73%
I listen to longer podcasts (over 15 minutes) for in-depth information	54%
I listen to short podcasts (under 15 minutes) to learn new things	52%
I search for hashtags related to what I'm interested in	30%
I join or create online communities where people share information	26%

Note: Sum of "Very likely" and "Likely" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "How do you usually find information about things that interest you online?".

German young people do not significantly differ from their counterparts in other countries in most of the preferences, but there are two cases in which they differ largely (see Figure 22). German youth seem to be very reluctant to join online communities in contrast to their counterparts from other countries (about 27% rate as overall likely in comparison with about 60% in their peers from other countries), and they also seem to be much less interested in using hashtags (about 30% of respondents consider it likely versus about 44% of peers abroad).

Figure 22: Preferences of searching for information in the online environment, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Use of social media in general

Given the omnipresence of social media in contemporary society, and especially in the lives of young people, the Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025 also explored this area in connection with mobility information. Young people in Germany use social media in general to a very similar extent (91%) as their peers from other countries (95%). When exploring social media platforms in more detail, it becomes apparent that the most used social media in German youth is Instagram, with almost 90% using it daily, followed by TikTok and YouTube used by almost half of young people (see Figure 23).

Figure 23: Summary overview of overall usage of social media platforms, among German youth.

Instagram	89%
TikTok	48%
YouTube	46%
Facebook	12%
X (formerly known as Twitter)	7%
Discord	7%
Threads	5%
Telegram	5%
Reddit	4%
LinkedIn	3%

Note: Sum of "Multiple times a day" and "Once a day" options is used as the indicator of the overall usage. The question read "How often do you use the following social media and/or messaging app?".

While young people from Germany use social media platforms to a similar extent as their fellows from other countries, they use some of the platforms less (see Figure 24). This is the case of Facebook (used by 13%, in contrast to 43% of their fellows), X (used by 8% of the German teens, compared with 19% teens using it on the European level), YouTube (utilized by 46% of the Germans and 59% of their peers), LinkedIn (used by 3% in Germany relative to 16% on the European level), and Telegram (overall used by 5%, in comparison with 14% of their peers from other countries). Moreover, there are much larger shares of young people from Germany who do not use many of these social networks at all, for example 73% do not use Facebook against only 29% of young people from other countries.

Figure 24: Usage of social media platforms, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries

Using social media to search for mobility information

Young people also had a chance to share their views on how likely it is that they will use each of the social media platforms for search of mobility-related information. All in all, German young people are most likely to use Instagram and YouTube in their search for mobility-related information, and about half of them are also likely to use TikTok. All other social media platforms are very marginal in German youth (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: Summary overview of usage of social media platforms for search of mobility-related information, among German youth.

Instagram	91%
YouTube	90%
TikTok	52%
Snapchat	12%
LinkedIn	9%
Reddit	8%
Facebook	8%
X (former Twitter)	6%
Discord	4%
Telegram	3%

Note: Sum of "Very likely" and "Likely" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Which social media and/or messaging app would you use to find information about going abroad?".

German youth have comparable preferences to their peers from other countries when it comes to using social media. About 90% of the German respondents preferred Instagram, while TikTok is preferred by about 50%. Snapchat, Reddit and Discord are rated by about 10% of the respondents as the preferred Social Media platform.

German young people are more likely to use YouTube when searching for mobility-related information, in comparison with their peers from other countries (about 90% rate as overall likely in comparison with about 76% in their peers from other countries; see Figure 26).

Most notably, however, German youth are less likely to use many of the social media platforms for mobility-related information search. This is in line with the generally lower usage of social media shown on the previous pages.

Only 8% of German youth would use Facebook for mobility-related information search, compared to 52% of their peers abroad), only 9% of German youth would use LinkedIn (versus 30% internationally), only 7% of German youth would use X (versus 20% of European peers), and only 3% of German youth would use Telegram (versus 15% of fellows abroad). These are considerable differences, and they should be reflected in the national information sharing efforts across Germany, especially those aimed at 16-23-year-olds (as these are mostly represented in the German sample).

Figure 26: Usage of social media platforms for mobility-related information search, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Young people from Germany are slightly less likely to doublecheck the information they find on social media (see Figure 27), with 75% of German youth claiming to often doublecheck information they found on social media (in comparison with 83% in their peers from other countries).

Figure 27: Doublechecking of information found on social media platforms, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

4. How did German young people experience mobility in 2022 and 2023?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on their direct mobility experiences. For overall results, refer to [the main report 2025](#).

In 2022 or 2023, 61% of young people from Germany did not participate in any mobility (the very same result as in their counterparts from other countries), and the remaining 39% of German youth experienced various mobilities (see Figure 28). German young people were more likely to go beyond the European borders, with 11% of them spending their mobility period outside of Europe, compared to 4% of their European peers. 24% of the German youth and 32% of the European youth would stay in one of the European countries. A comparable share of young people from Germany spent their mobility both in Europe and beyond (4% in contrast to 3%).

When it comes to those young people who did not experience mobility in 2022 or 2023, German young people do not differ from their peers from other countries. About 76% of them did not even plan any mobility stay in that period, and among those who did plan their mobility, the largest share of young people applied but was not selected (about 11%) or started the application process but did not complete it (about 10%).

Figure 28: Share of young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Use of different mobility types

Young people who went abroad in 2022 or 2023 were invited to share what mobility activity they attended. All in all, school exchanges were by far the most favourite mobility activity among young Germans in 2022 or 2023, with volunteering and DiscoverEU complementing the top three popular mobility types (see Figure 29). On the other hand, German young people were least likely to use au pair, summer schools, and trainings, workshops, or seminars.

German young people do not differ from their counterparts from other countries across many mobility types, such as volunteering, apprenticeships, au pair, work exchanges, university studies, summer schools, or DiscoverEU. German youth and young people from other countries use these types of mobility activities to the same or very similar extent.

There were three types of mobility activities in which young Germans participated substantially differently than their peers from other countries in 2022 or 2023. In school exchanges, there were more young people from Germany (33%) than among their fellows from other countries (19%). On the other hand, there were less young Germans in youth exchanges or youth camps (12% in comparison with 27% among their peers abroad) and in trainings, workshops, or seminars (7% in Germany compared to 24% in other countries).

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 also asked those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023 about the format of mobility experience they chose (see Figure 30). German young people used in-person mobility the most (93%), and hybrid and virtual experiences only marginally (8% and 3%, respectively). These results do not differ substantially from the results of young people from other countries.

Figure 29: Summary overview of mobility activities used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

School exchange	33%
Volunteering	19%
Travel via DiscoverEU	16%
Youth exchange or youth camp	12%
University/college study period abroad	12%
Work exchange programme (e.g. Woofing)	12%
Internship, traineeship or apprenticeship	11%
Training, workshop or seminar	7%
Summer school	4%
Au pair	4%

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "What did you do abroad?".

Figure 30: Summary overview of formats of mobility experience used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

In-person experience: travel to another country and have the full experience in person	93%
Hybrid experience: a mix of online and abroad activities	8%
Virtual experience: participation is entirely online	3%

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "What was the format of your mobility experience?".

Use of mobility programmes

Young people who went abroad in 2022 or 2023 were also invited to share with us what mobility schemes, if any, they used to support their mobility experience. All in all (see Figure 31), most of the young Germans did not use any mobility scheme to support their travels (60%), and the most used mobility schemes were Erasmus+ (19%), and the European Solidarity Corps (6%). It needs to be noted, that much more precise information on usage of various schemes should be available from the data collected by National Agencies for mobility programmes in each country.

Figure 31: Summary overview of mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

No	60%
Erasmus+	19%
I do not know	10%
European Solidarity Corps	6%
Erasmus for young entrepreneurs	3%
EU Youth Dialogue	1%
Interreg Volunteer Youth	1%

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "Did you benefit from any of these EU programmes for this mobility experience?".

German young people used some of the mobility schemes to the same or a very similar extent as their peers from other countries, and these include Erasmus for young entrepreneurs, European

Solidarity Corps, Interreg Volunteer Youth, and the EU Youth Dialogue. There were also very similar shares of young people from Germany and from outside Germany who did not know if they benefited from support of any of these mobility schemes (10% and 6%, respectively).

Figure 32: Mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

There were, however, two major differences between German youth and their counterparts from other European countries (see Figure 32). There were many more young people from Germany who claimed that they did not use any mobility scheme to support their time abroad (60%) than young people from abroad (20%), and there were many less young Germans who claimed to be using Erasmus+ (19%) compared to 60% of their peers. This result may be due to availability of other funding schemes that young people in Germany may use, such as the KJP (Kinder- und Jugendplan), or schemes run by various German ministries. That makes it hard for youth to know what the source of their funding is. Moreover, it needs to be noted that the survey did not have any means of verifying the respondents' claims, and therefore these results may be influenced by external factors, such as memory of the respondents, visibility of the Erasmus+ brand in the German context, and other. This limitation, of course, applies also to all support scheme-related findings below.

Use of Erasmus+

Young people who used Erasmus+ as their support mobility scheme were also asked for further details on what sub-action they used. All in all, among German young people supported by Erasmus+, there were three most commonly used sub-actions: mobility for students, DiscoverEU, and mobility for pupils and apprentices (see Figure 33). A surprising result can be seen in case of internships, since these are rather popular as a general mobility activity among German youth (see Figure 3 in Chapter 2). This may be due to lack of visibility of this particular Erasmus+ strand.

Figure 33: Summary overview of mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 and used Erasmus+ as the mobility support scheme, among German youth.

Mobility for students	37%
DiscoverEU	30%
Mobility for pupils and apprentices	26%
Youth Exchange	19%
Youth Participation Activity	13%
Internship abroad	12%

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "If 'Yes Erasmus+' please specify:".

Figure 34: Mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 and used Erasmus+ as the mobility support scheme, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries, part I.

Figure 35: Mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 and used Erasmus+ as the mobility support scheme, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries, part II.

German youth used some sub-actions to the same extent as their peers from other countries, these were: mobility for students, internships abroad, and youth participation activities. There were two strands that German young people used substantially more often than their. 26% of the German youth and 7% of the European youth utilized mobility programmes for pupils and apprentices, while 30% of Germans and 16% of their peers abroad travelled with DiscoverEU. Participation in youth exchanges was lower among German youth (19%) than among international peers (48%).

Use of the European solidarity corps

Young people were also given a chance to share more on their engagement within the European Solidarity Corps programme. All in all, individual volunteering was by far the most used European Solidarity Corps activity among German youth (see Figure 36).

Figure 36: Summary overview of mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 and used European Solidarity Corps as the mobility support scheme, among German youth.

Individual Volunteering	93%
Volunteering in a team	10%
Humanitarian Aid Volunteering	8%

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "If 'Yes European Solidarity Corps' please specify:".

German youth engaged to the same extent in Humanitarian Aid Volunteering activities as their peers from other countries (8%), but they engaged much more in the Individual Volunteering format (93%) than their peers from other countries (61%), and much less in Volunteering in Teams (10% in comparison with 45% in their counterparts from other countries; see Figure 37).

Figure 37: Mobility schemes used by young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 and used European Solidarity Corps as the mobility support scheme, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Sources of information supporting 2022 and 2023 mobilities

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 also offered those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023 an opportunity to share how they learned about the mobility opportunity they used. All in all (see Figure 38), the most used sources of information among the German young people that went abroad in 2022 or 2023 were family and relatives, schools and universities, social media, specialised websites, and peers or classmates.

Figure 38: Summary overview of sources of mobility-related information in young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Note: Sum of "Yes" answers. The question read "How did you find out about your mobility opportunity?".

German young people mostly do not differ from their peers from other countries in their use of information sources. The only two information sources that German young people use substantially differently (see Figure 39) are relatives and family members, which German youth rely on much more than young people from other European countries (38% compared to 18%), and social media which young people from Germany use less than their counterparts from other countries (30% in comparison to 41%).

Figure 39: Sources of mobility-related information in young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Motivation factors

Young people also shared their motivations for going abroad in 2022 or 2023. All in all (see Figure 40), German youth was most motivated to go abroad in 2022 or 2023 by seeking fun and new experiences, getting away from daily routines, and doing something meaningful and useful.

Figure 40: Summary overview of motivations of young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

I wanted to have fun, live a new experience	99%
I wanted to get away from my daily routines	94%
I wanted to do something meaningful and useful	91%
I wanted to increase my employability	67%
My friends motivated me to do it	43%
It was part of my education	22%
My parents wanted me to do it	18%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "What was your motivation to go abroad?".

Young people from Germany were just as likely as their peers from other countries to be motivated by getting away from the daily routines, by wanting to have fun and live a new experience, by wanting to do something meaningful and useful, and encouraged by friends.

Young people from Germany were much less motivated to go abroad by external obligations (see Figure 41), such as school curricula (only 22% of the Germans and 69% of their fellows went abroad because it was part of their education). Only 17% of German youth feel less motivated to go abroad due to family expectations, compared with 32% at the European level. Employability was also less of a motivator in German youth (67%) than in their peers (86%).

Figure 41: Motivations of young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Application process

Young people were also asked about support they received when drafting their mobility applications. All in all (see Figure 42), German youth mostly did not need any support with their applications, and those who did mostly sought it in their families. Given that the shares of those who went abroad among German youth was the same as among their peers from other countries, it is reasonable to assume that young people from Germany are not negatively affected by not seeking support.

Figure 42: Summary overview of support in drafting mobility applications of young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

No, I did not need support	44%
Yes, from a parent / relative	38%
Yes, from a teacher / professor	15%
Yes, from a friend	12%
Yes, from a counsellor / information worker	8%
Yes, I used AI to draft the application	3%

Note: Share of "Yes" answers. The question read "Did you receive some help when drafting your mobility application(s)?".

German youth did not differ largely from their peers in other countries, with only one exception: receiving help from parents or relatives (38% of the German youth agreed compared to only 15% of young people abroad). For the information services, the importance of a family unit as an information source should be noticed (see Figure 43).

German young people also did not differ from their peers in other countries in one important aspect: they enjoyed their mobility stays immensely, with 69% stating it was an amazing experience, and further 26% describing it as a good experience. German young people would also be just as likely as their peers from other countries to encourage others to go for a mobility experience, which further signals high satisfaction levels. In total, 97% agreed that they would encourage others to go for a mobility experience of their own.

Figure 43: Support in drafting mobility applications of young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Mobility experience satisfaction and impact

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 also offered those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023 an opportunity to share what specifically they gained because of that experience. All in all (see Figure 44), German young people show high levels of developments across many different areas, with the most pronounced being increased awareness of other cultures and values, boost in self-confidence, increase in open-mindedness, stimulations in foreign language domain, and feeling inspired to share their experiences with others.

Figure 44: Summary overview of developments in young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Increased your awareness of other cultures and values	96%
Boosted your self-confidence	93%
Made you feel more open-minded	93%
Stimulated your curiosity about foreign languages	91%
Inspired you to share your experiences with others	90%
Increased your desire to live abroad	81%
Enhanced your sense of European identity	81%
Enhanced your employability	78%
Increased your capacity to make friends easily	76%
Piqued your interest in European topics	74%
Increased your engagement in social matters (e.g. volunteering)	72%
Increased your involvement in political affairs	58%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Do you agree or disagree that taking part in these activities...".

German young people show the same or very similar levels of developments in many areas, such as increase in awareness of other cultures and values, in curiosity about foreign languages, in self-confidence, in a desire to live abroad, in employability, in being open-minded, in involvement in political affairs, in making friends, or in sharing experiences with others. There were, however, some domains in which German youth claimed less impacts than their peers in other countries (see Figure 45). These areas of development include engagement in social matters (72% of German youth versus 85% of their peers abroad), enhanced sense of European identity (80% versus 91%), interest in European topics (75% versus 89%).

Figure 45: Developments in young people who went abroad for a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

5. What mobility challenges do young people identify?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 offered young people space to share their opinions on challenges they faced when going through their mobility experience or when thinking about organising it. For overall results, see [the main report 2025](#).

Reasons for not going abroad

Young people who did not take part in any mobility experience in 2022 or 2023 were asked about the reasons for not participating. All in all (see Figure 46), by far the most frequent reason for not going abroad in 2022 or 2023 was lack of time. This is an opportunity for the youth information services, since guidance and good practice examples of negotiating time restraints with mobility experiences can be shared with young people to encourage them in going abroad.

Figure 46: Summary overview of reasons for not participating in a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

I did not have time	46%
I did not think about it back then	18%
I did not know how to do this	16%
I am not or I was not eligible	13%
Nobody has ever informed me about these possibilities	13%
I thought it was not for me	8%
I do not know	6%
I was not interested	4%

Note: Share of "Yes" answers. The question read "Why haven't you taken part in mobility activities? Please select all answers that apply."

In comparison with their peers from other countries, the same or very similar shares of German young people stated that they did not know why they did not participate, that they did not know how to do that, that they thought it was not for them, that they did not even think about such opportunities, or that they were not interested. In other words, all these reasons were just as common among the German youth as they were among young people from other countries.

On the other hand (see Figure 47), German young people were more likely to state that they did not have time (46%) than their peers (23%), and less likely to say that they did not know have information about mobilities (13% versus 29%).

Figure 47: Reasons for not participating in a mobility experience in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Challenges for mobility

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 offered young people space to share their opinions on challenges related to mobility. Those who participated in mobility in 2022 or 2023 were asked about the challenges they experienced, and those who did not go abroad in 2022 or 2023 were asked about challenges that prevented them from going.

The first set of challenges focused on those which occurred when accessing mobility programmes. It is obvious (see Figure 48 and Figure 49) that the four main issues were identified identically by those German young people who went abroad and by those who did not: financial challenges, lack of information, administrative problems, and problems in finding opportunities for which one is eligible. It is also apparent that the challenges were identified by larger shares of those German youth with no mobility experience, when compared to those who actually went abroad. For example, while 62% of German youth without mobility experience fear lack of information, only 36% of the young Germans with mobility experience state that it was a challenge for them when they were preparing for traveling abroad. In other words, while the four key challenges were identified by both groups, they did not occur in reality as often as they were feared.

Interestingly, German young people and their peers from other countries had largely comparable views when it came to this set of challenges, with only one exception: availability of opportunities from the point of view of those who did not go abroad (see Figure 50). 74% of German youth felt there were no available opportunities, and that prevented them from going abroad, compared to 55% of their European peers.

Figure 48: Summary overview of challenges in accessing the mobility programmes, as faced by those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Financial problems to cover the costs	48%
Lack of information	36%
Administrative problems	34%
Matching the eligibility criteria	24%
Discouragement from my family	19%
Discouragement from my friends	15%
Discrimination (e.g. race, gender, age, disability)	12%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes?" and it was asked to those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Figure 49: Summary overview of challenges preventing young people from going abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Unavailable opportunities	74%
Lack of information	62%
Financial problems	56%
Administrative problems	30%
Discouragement from my family	22%
Stay abroad did not fit my personality	18%
Discouragement from my friends	9%
Discrimination (e.g. race, gender, age, disability)	6%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Did any of the following problems prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023?" and it was asked to those who did not go abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Figure 50: Challenges preventing young people from going abroad in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

Barriers during a mobility experience

The second set of challenges focused on those which occurred during the mobility experience, either when traveling, or when living abroad. Both groups of German young people, those with and those without mobility experience, identified the same three key challenges (see Figure 51 and Figure 52): getting out of the comfort zone (also labelled as unfamiliarity with daily life abroad), lack of language skills, and fears related to fitting in (making new friends).

While in most of the challenges, there were no substantial differences between German youth and their counterparts from other countries, there were three exceptions (see Figure 53). About 51% of young people with mobility experience from Germany were more frequently facing the challenge of leaving their comfort zone compared to 38% of their peers. Young people without mobility experience from Germany were more worried about losing touch with friends (35%) and not making new friends (45%) compared to their fellows (21% and 32%, respectively).

Figure 51: Summary overview of challenges occurring during mobility periods, as faced by those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth, part I.

Getting out of my comfort zone	52%
Lack of language skills	37%
Difficulties in making new friends	37%
Physical health problems during the stay	27%
Mental health problems during the stay	26%
Difficulties to travel abroad	25%
Lack of leisure time activities during the stay	24%
Lack of communication with my friends	23%
Difficulties in adapting to a new culture	22%
Problems with a hosting institution	22%
Lack of understanding of how things work abroad	17%
Lack of communication with my family	16%
Long-term health problems	8%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Did you face any of the following difficulties when moving or living abroad?" and it was asked to those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Figure 52: Summary overview of challenges preventing young people from going abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth, part II.

Fear of not making friends	45%
Language barrier	40%
Unfamiliarity with daily life abroad	38%
Losing touch with my friends	34%
Travel-related problems	25%
Mental health issues	23%
Fear of not adapting to a new culture	23%
Losing touch with my family	19%
Losing access to leisure activities	19%
Problems with a hosting institution	14%
Physical health issues	11%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Did any of the following reasons prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023?" and it was asked to those who did not go abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Figure 53: Challenges in going abroad in 2022 or 2023, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries, part III.

Challenges of coming back from a mobility experience

The third and last set of challenges focused on those which occurred when coming back to the home country. Overall, there were two key challenges which were identified by both the German youth with and without the mobility experience (see Figure 54 and Figure 55). Missing out on opportunities was the first principal challenge, feared by 49% of those who did not go abroad, and faced by 21% of those who did. Prolonging of studies was the second principal challenge, feared by 43% of those with no mobility experience, and faced by 19% of those who went abroad. German youth and their peers from other countries did not substantially differ in their assessment of these challenges, in other words, German youth and their peers viewed these challenges very similarly.

Figure 54: Summary overview of challenges occurring after mobility periods, as faced by those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Missing out on opportunities	21%
Prolonging of studies	19%
Family issues during the stay	13%
Housing difficulties	11%
Loss of social security	11%
Lack of family support	9%
Loss of employment	6%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Did your stay abroad cause any difficulties when returning to your home country?" and it was asked to those who went abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Figure 55: Summary overview of challenges preventing young people from going abroad in 2022 or 2023, among German youth.

Missing out on opportunities	49%
Prolonging of studies	43%
Family issues during the stay	24%
Loss of social security	22%
Loss of employment	21%
Housing difficulties	20%
Lack of family support	18%

Note: Sum of "Strongly agree" and "Agree" options is used as the indicator of the overall preferences. The question read "Were you worried that your stay abroad would cause any of the following difficulties in your life when returning to your home country?" and it was asked to those who did not go abroad in 2022 or 2023.

Lastly, young people were asked about culture shock and reverse culture shock. German young people did not differ in their experience of culture (45%) and reverse culture (47%) shocks in comparison with their peers from other countries. Young people from Germany were, however, more aware when it comes to culture shock, with about 95% of them claiming they have heard the term, whereas about 82% of their peers know about the phenomenon (see Figure 56). There was no difference in awareness of the term reverse culture shock between German and European youth (about 39%).

Figure 56: Awareness of culture shock phenomena, comparison of German youth and their peers from other countries.

6. Conclusions

Young people from Germany are just as open to going abroad as their peers from other countries, and they are more likely to go beyond the borders of Europe for their mobility stays. Moreover, when young people from Germany do go abroad, they are just as thrilled about the experience as their peers from other countries. Young Germans are, however, more worried about the environmental impacts of their travels, and they are also a bit less enthusiastic about the benefits of a mobility experience to various domains of their lives. Young Germans are motivated most by having fun, doing something new and meaningful, and getting away from daily routines, with external pressures (school obligations, push from families, etc.) being much less effective motivators.

Young people from Germany are enthusiastic to go travelling in general, to do an internship abroad, or to work abroad, and they are also happy to study internationally. They are most prone to going abroad for 1-6 months, and they are very aligned with their peers from other countries on the preferred mobility format, which is in-person mobility.

Challenges perceived as most pressing among the German youth are time restraints, finances, finding opportunities for which one is eligible, and lack of information in general. On top of these, German youth seem to be more prone to be reluctant to get out of their comfort zone, and to leave behind their friends, than their peers abroad. These are all domains in which information services could support young people from Germany to manage their expectations, fears, and resources in such a way that their mobility experience is the best possible.

When searching for mobility-related information, Eurodesk is more known by German youth than by young people from other countries, but other EU-wide initiatives such as EURES, or Europe Direct, lack attention among German youth in comparison with their peers from elsewhere. German young people also seem to be less fond of youth information services and youth organisations when searching for mobility-related information. This is, of course, an important finding for the youth sector in Germany, since it suggests that information outreach may not be as wide as in other countries, and that if the youth sector is to be an effective and efficient information provider, its visibility among the German youth might need to be increased. This boost in visibility might be best achieved by using information sources favoured by German youth. These are Eurodesk, schools and universities, and most importantly peers, families and parents. Peers and the family are seen as an important information source by German young people in the

domain of finding out information, but also in assisting with mobility applications. As an example, youth (information) services might team up with formal education providers in information campaigns, and opportunities to reach out directly to parents or whole families could be sought or invented (e.g., open doors days, attending or creating events for parents or whole families, utilising information campaigns aiming directly at parents, etc.).

Web search and social media are, however, one of the most prominent information sources for both German youth and their peers from other countries. The online environments are diverse, and some of them are not used much by the German young people when looking for mobility related information, such as messaging apps, online communities, or hashtags. These are therefore likely to bring very limited outreach to any youth-focused information campaign on mobility. On the other hand, general web search, online videos, and social media are highly popular with German youth.

When it comes to social media use, German young people are surprisingly almost ignoring Facebook, X (former Twitter), and LinkedIn, while being very present on Instagram, and using TikTok and YouTube to a high extent. The attractiveness of videos for German young people also show when asked about looking for mobility related information on social media, with German young people using YouTube much more than their peers from other countries. It should also be noted that young people from Germany are more likely to find out about mobility opportunities from social media than their European peers, and therefore social media may present an effective youth information channel.

Lastly, it needs to be reiterated that while the German survey sample was large (1878 responses) and while it was comparable with the general sample in all measured background variables (e.g., minority background, size of settlement where young people lived, etc.), it mostly consisted of young people aged 16-23. This fact calls for careful interpretation of the presented findings, especially when providing youth information services to different age groups.

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